

Cobalt-Dimethyl Glyoxime Chelate: A Physical Study

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That cobalt (II) forms a chelate with dimethyl glyoxime solution in 1:2 ratio has been confirmed by refractometric method. Conductometric and spectrophotometric measurements using 66% ethanolic solution also lead to the same conclusion.

Kenjiro *et al.*¹ observed complex salt formation for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} with ethanolic solutions of dimethyl glyoxime (hereafter abbreviated as Dmg) by spectroscopic method from the position of maxima. Ablov² studied the complex formation with CoCl_2 , Dmg, and various mono-substituted aniline derivatives and reported the formation of complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{RNH}_2)\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{RNH}_2)_2\text{Cl}]$, where DH_2 stands for Dmg.

In our study of the chelate formation between cobalt sulphate and dimethyl glyoxime solution, the wave lengths selected were 370, 380 and 390 μ . Absorbance of the mixtures and of Dmg and of cobalt sulphate solutions of that strength present in the mixture were measured at a constant temperature. Job's method³ of continued variation was adopted in preparing mixtures. The difference in absorbance of the mixture and sum of absorbances due to the two components was plotted against value of one of the components—Dmg of a particular strength. From the peak of the curve, the composition of the chelate was arrived at. The total volume of the mixture in each case was made to 10 ml. The results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The results show that the composition of the chelate is 2:1 of Dmg: Co(II) which is in agreement with that of other workers.

Refractive index measurements have shown the existence of transition temperature in case of solutions of sodium carbonate, magnesium sulphate, sodium sulphate, and zinc sulphate⁴. This method has been applied to study the chelate formation between Co(II) salt solution and Dmg solution in 66% ethanol, adopting the monovariation method⁵ in the preparation of mixtures. This method has limitations in the sense that neither very concentrated solutions due to precipitation of the complex nor very dilute ones because of the too small variation of the refractive index for the instrument to record, can be used. In our study, the strengths of the solutions that gave satisfactory results were Dmg, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and cobalt sulphate, of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$; the volume of cobalt sulphate solution was fixed at 5.0 ml and the total volume was made to 15.0 ml in the case of (A) and 20.0 ml in the case of (B). From the data graphs were plotted as shown in Fig. 3(A) and 3(B). The inflections in these graphs confirm the composition of the chelate as Dmg: Co(II)=2:1.

1. *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1933, 54, 1.

2. *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 4354.

3. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

4. Joshi and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 149; 1958, 35, 553.

5. Nayar and Pande, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284.

FIG. 1

A ₁ :	370 mμ ;	Co(II) SO ₄ =	1 × 10 ⁻³ M
B ₁ :	380	" "	" "
C ₁ :	390	" "	" "
D ₁ :	370	" "	25 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
E ₁ :	380	" "	" "
F ₁ :	390	" "	" "

COBALT-DIMETHYL GLYOXIME CHELATE

FIG. 2

A ₂ :	370 ml ^l :	Dmg. conc. $5 \times 10^{-3} M$;	Co(II) SO ₄ = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$
B ₂ :	380	"	" "
C ₂ :	390	"	" "
D ₂ :	390	"	" "
E ₂ :	380	"	" "
F ₂ :	390	"	" "
		$25 \times 10^{-4} M$	$25 \times 10^{-4} M$

FIG. 3

- A: Dmg = $2 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 Co(II) $SO_4 = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$
 B: Dmg = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 Co(II) $SO_4 = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$

Measurements of conductance were carried out by taking a fixed amount of cobalt sulphate solution (5 ml) and adding various amounts of Dmg solution. The volume was made large enough by adding 150 ml of conductivity water to the cobalt sulphate solution. Solutions of Dmg used were of strengths $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ and of cobalt sulphate, $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. From the data, graphs were plotted as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The inflections lead to the same conclusion that the composition of the chelate is as 2:1 of Dmg: Co(II). By using cobalt chloride and Dmg in acetone solution, Babko and Korotun⁶ from conductometric titrations have shown the complex to have the formula $H[Co(Dmg)_2Cl_2]$.

FIG. 4

- Dmg = $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 Co(II) $SO_4 = 1.35 \times 10^{-2} M$

COBALT-DIMETHYL GLYOXIME CHELATE

FIG. 5

Dmg. = $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\text{Co(II)SO}_4 = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt sulphate and dimethyl glyoxime were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality and the same sample of conductivity (10.1×10^{-6} mho) water was used in all measurements. $M/20$ cobalt sulphate^o was prepared as a stock solution and other solutions were obtained from this by dilution. The chelating agent, Dmg., of strength $M/20$ was also prepared as a stock solution by making its 66% ethanolic solution.

Ethanol was purified by distilling twice, once after adding some lime and next by adding a couple of sodium pieces.

The refractometric study was made by means of an Abbe refractometer, able to read refractive index to ± 0.0001 . Temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

Conductivity data were collected by using Serfass Conductivity Bridge (3695), model R.C.M. 15 B.L. in which the monovariation method was adopted. The volume of cobalt sulphate solution was kept constant and that of dimethyl glyoxime kept varying. To this an excess of conductivity water was added to minimise the volume error. The temperature was kept constant at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ by means of a 'Gallenkamp thermostat'.

Absorbance measurements were made by means of 'Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer'. The absorbance measurements were made by keeping the mixtures for some period as the complex took some time to attain equilibrium.